

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 74

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 74

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 74:0 A †Maskil of Asaph.</p>	<p>Psa. 74:1 מִשְׁכֵּיל לְאָסָף לְמַה</p>
<p>Psa. 74:1 O God, why have You “rejected us forever?</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים זָנַחְתָּ לְנִצָּחַת יַעֲשֶׂן</p>
<p>Why does Your anger ^bsmoke against the ‘sheep of Your ¹pasture?</p>	<p>אָפֶךָ בְּצֹאן מִרְעִיתֶךָ : 2 זְכֹר</p>
<p>² Remember Your congregation, which You have ^apurchased of old,</p>	<p>עַד־תֶּךָ קָנִיתָ קִדְמָה גְּאֻלָּתָהּ</p>
<p>Which You have ^bredeemed to be the ‘tribe of Your inheritance;</p>	<p>שָׁבַט נִחַלְתֶּךָ הַר־צִיּוֹן זֶה </p>
<p><i>And</i> this Mount ^dZion, where You have dwelt.</p>	<p>שְׁכַנְתָּ בּוֹ : 3 הָרִימָה בְּעַמֶּיךָ לְמִשְׁאֹת נִצַּח כָּל־הַרְע</p>
<p>³ ¹Turn Your footsteps toward the ^aperpetual ruins;</p>	<p>אוֹיֵב בְּקִדְשׁ : 4 שְׁאֲנוּ צִרְרֶיךָ</p>
<p>The enemy ^bhas damaged everything within the sanctuary.</p>	<p>בְּקֶרֶב מוֹעֵדֶךָ שָׁמוּ אוֹתָתָם</p>
<p>⁴ Your adversaries have ^aroared in the midst of Your meeting place;</p>	<p>אֵתוֹת : 5 יוֹדַע כְּמִבִּיא</p>
<p>They have set up their ^bown ¹standards ^cfor signs.</p>	<p>לְמַעַלָּה בְּסִבְךָ־עֵץ</p>
<p>⁵ It seems as if one had lifted up <i>His</i> ^{1a}axe in a ²forest of trees.</p>	<p>קָרָדְמוֹת : 6 וְעַתָּה [וְ] [עֲפָתָה]</p>
<p>⁶ And now ¹all its ^acarved work</p>	<p>פְּתוּחֶיהָ יִחַד בְּכִשְׁלִיל</p>
<p>They smash with hatchet and ²hammers.</p>	<p>וְכִילֹפֶת יַהֲלִמוּן : 7 שְׁלֹתָהּ</p>
<p>⁷ They have ^{1a}burned Your sanctuary ²to the ground;</p>	<p>בְּאֵשׁ מִקְדָּשְׁךָ לְאַרְץ חֲלָלָהּ</p>
<p>They have ^bdefiled the dwelling place of Your name.</p>	<p>מִשְׁכַּן־שִׁמְךָ : 8 אָמְרוּ בְּלִבָּם</p>
<p>⁸ They ^asaid in their heart, “Let us ¹completely ²subdue them.”</p>	<p>נִינָם יִחַד שָׂרְפּוּ כָּל־מוֹעֲדֵי־</p>
<p>They have burned all the meeting places of God in the land.</p>	<p>אֵל בְּאֶרֶץ : 9 אוֹתֵינוּ לֹא</p>
<p>⁹ We do not see our ^asigns; There is ^bno longer any prophet,</p>	<p>רְאֵינוּ אֵין־עוֹד נְבִיא וְלֹא־ אֲתָנוּ יָדַע עַד־מָה : 10 עַד־</p>

Nor is there any among us who knows ⁴how long.

¹⁰ How long, O God, will the adversary ^arevile,

And the enemy ^bspurn Your name forever?

¹¹ Why ^ado You withdraw Your hand, even Your right hand?

From within Your bosom, ^bdestroy them!

Psa. 74:12 Yet God is ^amy king from of old,

Who works deeds of deliverance in the midst of the earth.

¹³ ¹You ^adivided the sea by Your strength;

¹You ^bbroke the heads of the ³sea monsters ²in the waters.

¹⁴ ¹You crushed the heads of ^{2a}Leviathan;

¹You gave him as food for the ³creatures ^bof the wilderness.

¹⁵ ¹You ^abroke open springs and torrents;

¹You ^bdried up ever-flowing streams.

¹⁶ Yours is the day, Yours also is the night;

¹You have ^aprepared the ²light and the sun.

¹⁷ ¹You have ^aestablished all the boundaries of the earth;

¹You have ²made ^bsummer and winter.

Psa. 74:18 Remember this, ¹O LORD, that the enemy has ^areviled,

And a ^bfoolish people has spurned Your name.

מִתִּי אֱלֹהִים יִתְרַף צַר יִנְאֹץ

אוֹיֵב שְׂמִיךָ לְנִצַּח : ¹¹ לְמָה

תָּשִׁיב יָדְךָ וַיִּמְיֶנְךָ מִקְרֹב

חֹקֶךָ [תִּיקֶנְךָ] כִּלְהָ : ¹²

וְאֱלֹהִים מִלְּכִי מִקְדָּם פָּעַל

יְשׁוּעוֹת בְּקִרְבִּי הָאָרֶץ : ¹³

אַתָּה פּוֹרְרָת בְּעֵזְבֵי יָם

שְׂבָרָתָ רָאשֵׁי תַנִּינִים עַל-

הַיָּם : ¹⁴ אַתָּה רִצַּצְתָּ רָאשֵׁי

לְוִיתָן תַּתְּנַנּוּ מֵאֲכָל לְעַם

לְצִיִּים : ¹⁵ אַתָּה בִקַּעְתָּ מַעֲיָן

וְנַחַל אַתָּה הוֹבִשְׁתָּ נְהַרוֹת

אֵיתָן : ¹⁶ לָךְ יוֹם אֶף-לָךְ

לַיְלָה אַתָּה הִכִּינֹתָ מְאוֹר

וְשֶׁמֶשׁ : ¹⁷ אַתָּה הִצַּבְתָּ כָּל-

גְּבוּלוֹת אֶרֶץ קִיץ וְחֹרֶף

אַתָּה יִצְרַתָּם : ¹⁸ זְכַר-זֹאת

אוֹיֵב תִּרְרַף אִיהוּהָ וְעַם נָכַל

נִאֲצוּ שְׂמִיךָ : ¹⁹ אֶל-תִּתֵּן

לְתִית נִפְשׁ תוֹרְךָ תִּית עֲנִיִּיךָ

אֶל-תִּשְׁכַּח לְנִצַּח : ²⁰ הַגִּבֹּט

לְבָרִית כִּי מָלְאוּ מִחֲשָׁכִי-

אֶרֶץ נְאוֹת תִּמָּס : ²¹ אֶל-יִשָּׁב

¹⁹ Do not deliver the soul of Your
"turtledove to the wild beast;

^bDo not forget the life of Your
afflicted forever.

²⁰ Consider the "covenant;
For the ^bdark places of the land are
full of the habitations of violence.

²¹ Let not the "oppressed return
dishonored;

Let the ^bafflicted and needy praise
Your name.

Psa. 74:22 Arise, O God, *and*
"plead Your own cause;

Remember ¹how the ^bfoolish man
reproaches You all day long.

²³ Do not forget the voice of Your
"adversaries,

The ^buproar of those who rise
against You which ascends continually.

בְּדָךְ נִכְלַם עֵינֵי אֲבִיוֹן יִהְיֶה לָּךְ
שִׁמְךָ : ²² קוֹמָה אֱלֹהִים

רִיבָה רִיבָה זְכֹר חֲרַפְתֶּךָ
מִנֵּי-נִכְל כָּל-הַיּוֹם : ²³ אֵל-

תִּשְׁכַּח קוֹל צִרְרֶיךָ שְׁאוֹן
לְמִיךָ עֲלֶה תִמְיֵד :

References

Psalm 74:0

[†]Possibly, *Contemplative*, or *Didactic*, or *Skillful Psalm*

Psalm 74:1

¹Or *pasturing*

^aPs 44:9; 77:7

^bDeut 29:20; Ps 18:8; 89:46

^cPs 79:13; 95:7; 100:3

Psalm 74:2

^aEx 15:16; Deut 32:6

^bEx 15:13; Ps 77:15; 106:10; Is 63:9

^cDeut 32:9; Is 63:17; Jer 10:16; 51:19

^dPs 9:11; 68:16

Psalm 74:3

¹Lit *Lift up*

^aIs 61:4

^bPs 79:1

Psalm 74:4

¹Lit *signs*

^aLam 2:7

^bNum 2:2

^cPs 74:9

Psalm 74:5

¹Lit *axes*

²Lit *thicket*

^aJer 46:22

Psalm 74:6

¹Lit *altogether*

²Or *axes*

^{a1} Kin 6:18, 29, 32, 35

Psalm 74:7

¹Lit *set on fire*

²Or *To the ground they...*

^a2 Kin 25:9

^bPs 89:39; Lam 2:2

Psalm 74:8

¹Lit *altogether*

²Or *oppress*

^aPs 83:4

Psalm 74:9

^aPs 78:43

^{b1} Sam 3:1; Lam 2:9; Ezek 7:26; Amos 8:11

^cPs 6:3; 79:5; 80:4

Psalm 74:10

^aPs 44:16; 79:12; 89:51

^bLev 24:16

Psalm 74:11

^aLam 2:3

^bPs 59:13

Psalm 74:12

^aPs 44:4

Psalm 74:13

¹Or *You Yourself*

²Lit *on*

^aEx 14:21; Ps 78:13

^bIs 51:9

^cPs 148:7; Jer 51:34

Psalm 74:14

¹Or *You Yourself*

²Or *sea monster*

³Lit *people*

^aJob 41:1; Ps 104:26; Is 27:1

^bPs 72:9

Psalm 74:15

¹Or *You Yourself*

^aEx 17:5, 6; Num 20:11; Ps 78:15; 105:41; 114:8; Is 48:21

^bEx 14:21, 22; Josh 2:10; 3:13; Ps 114:3

Psalm 74:16

¹Or *You Yourself*

²Or *luminary*

^aGen 1:14-18; Ps 104:19; 136:7, 8

Psalm 74:17

¹Or *You Yourself*

²Or *formed*

^aDeut 32:8; Acts 17:26

^bGen 8:22; Ps 147:16-18

Psalm 74:18

¹Or *that the enemy has reviled the LORD*

^aPs 74:10

^bDeut 32:6; Ps 14:1; 39:8; 53:1

Psalm 74:19

^aSong 2:14

^bPs 9:18

Psalm 74:20

^aGen 17:7; Ps 106:45

^bPs 88:6; 143:3

Psalm 74:21

^aPs 103:6

^bPs 35:10; Is 41:17

Psalm 74:22

¹Lit *Your reproach from the foolish man*

^aPs 43:1; Is 3:13; 43:26; Ezek 20:35

^bPs 14:1; 53:1; 74:18

Psalm 74:23

^aPs 74:10

^bPs 65:7

Targum

Psa. 74:1 A good lesson, composed by Asaph. Why, O God, have you moved far off forever? [Why] will your anger be fierce against the flock of your pasture? ² Remember your congregation that you acquired of old; you redeemed from Egypt the tribes of your inheritance, this same Mount Zion on which you made your presence to abide. ³ Lift up your footsteps to dissolve the nations forever, for the enemy with all his strength has done harm in the holy place. ⁴ Your oppressors cry out in the midst of your assemblies; they have set up their standards as signs. ⁵ He will strike with a hammer like a man who lifts up his hand against a wood thicket to cut it with axes. ⁶ But now they pull down its carvings together; they pound with the hatchet and the two-edged chisel as if with mallets. ⁷ They have burned the sanctuary to the ground with fire; they have defiled the tabernacle in which your name is uttered. ⁸ Their children spoke in their hearts together; their fathers burned all the assemblies of God in the land. ⁹ We have not seen our signs that the prophets gave us; there are no longer any prophets and we have none with us who knows how long. ¹⁰ How long, O God, will the oppressor show disdain? Will the enemy reject your name forever? ¹¹ Why will you withdraw your hand, even your right hand, from redeeming? Take it out of your bosom and do away with oppression. ¹² But God is the king, whose holy presence is from of old, one who carries out redemption in the midst of the land. ¹³ You cut off the waters of the sea by your power; you broke the heads of the sea serpents, and drowned the Egyptians at the sea. ¹⁴ You shattered the heads of Pharaoh's warriors; you handed them over for destruction to the people of the house of Israel, and their corpses to jackals. ¹⁵ You split the spring from the rock and it became a stream; you dried up the ford of the streams of the Arnon and the ford of the Jabbok and the Jordan, which were so powerful. ¹⁶ Yours is the day-time, yours, too, is the night; you have made firm the moon and sun. ¹⁷ You set up all the boundaries of the earth; summer and winter, you created them. ¹⁸ Remember this, the enemy, slanderer of the LORD, and the foolish people who have rejected your name. ¹⁹ Do not deliver the souls of those who teach your Torah to the Gentiles, who are likened to beasts of the field; do not forget the lives of your poor forever. ²⁰ Look at the covenant that you made with our fathers, for their children are finished off; darkness is spread over the land, and fraud, and violence. ²¹ The pauper will not return ashamed; the poor and lowly will praise your name. ²² Arise, O God; argue your case; call to mind the disgrace of your people because of foolish counsel all the day. ²³ Do not forget the voice of your oppressors, the turmoil, always mounting, of those who stand against you.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The question of why righteous people suffer was covered in Psalm 73. The Psalmist studies the most painful example of the apparent injustice, the pitiful flight of the Jews in Exile. Assaf, the Psalmist, protested against the strictness of the LORD's judgment and questioned its equity. The LORD told Assaf that it was the Jews who abandoned Him when they stopped following the Torah. The Ten Commandments state that the LORD will watch over Israel if they follow the LORD's Torah.

Verse four

The Psalmist reminds the LORD that it was the enemies of Him who invaded and destroyed His Temple in Jerusalem. This is important to understand today. Many members and attendees of synagogues and churches are proving to be the enemies of the institution and, thus, enemies of the LORD. The people must believe in the LORD's ways and treat each other with respect and love. When people play power games for their own glory, they sully the name of the LORD.

It was as Your oppressors raged in the midst of Your meeting place; they have set up their signs as signs.

Verse eight

The enemies of the LORD who destroyed the Temple did so that the Jewish people would abandon the LORD. People in synagogue and church who strive for power for themselves and not for the LORD are doing the same thing the Babylonians did. They are burning down the LORD's meeting place. How many synagogues and churches have closed because power struggles overtook worship to the LORD? It is a large

number. The infighting within Christian denominations has caused membership drops. When members realize that their leaders are in it for themselves, they leave. Many stop attending a synagogue or church because they believe they will find the same situation in the new place similar to the situation they left. If this continues, our future generations will not have places to worship and will thus not learn about the LORD.

They have said in their heart, “Their future generations, altogether.” Thus they have burned up all the meeting places of God upon the earth.

Verse twenty-one

The Psalmist asks the LORD to answer a plea for help from the poor and powerless. He prays for intervention on their behalf. He also prays for the tyrants of the world to be crushed. Tyrants do not follow the Laws and Ways of the Torah. The poor and powerless should be protected and not exploited in the past, the present, or the future.

O let the crushed one not turn back in shame. Give the poor and defenseless cause to proclaim the praise of Your Name.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

